

TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF HEAT PUMP AND PHASE CHANGE MATERIAL-BASED THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE INTEGRATION**Burak İZGİ**

Yozgat Bozok University, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Yozgat-Türkiye (Responsible Author) ORCID: 0000-0001-9491-8653

Hüseyin Zahit DEMİR AĞ

Yozgat Bozok University, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Yozgat-Türkiye ORCID: 0000-0001-7289-4021

Mevlüt ARSLAN

Yozgat Bozok University, Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Yozgat-Türkiye ORCID: 0000-0003-4415-6202

Abstract

The integration of latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) systems with air-source heat pumps offers significant potential for increasing energy efficiency and shifting peak loads in residences, particularly in regions with time-of-use tariffs. This strategy aims to reduce consumption during expensive peak hours. This study numerically investigates a system configuration where high-grade heat from the air-source heat pump's condenser is stored in a Phase Change Material (PCM) unit during low-demand off-peak hours, when electricity tariffs are cheap. This stored latent heat is subsequently discharged to meet the building's heating load during peak hours, when electricity cost is high, thereby significantly reducing the heat pump's concurrent electrical consumption. In this work, the techno-economic performance of this integrated system is evaluated via a developed quasi-steady-state simulation model. The system is analyzed according to a tariff-aware control logic, and its performance is compared against a conventional baseline system using only a heat pump. Key performance indicators considered in the analysis include the total amount of electrical load shifted from expensive peak hours to cheap off-peak hours, variations in the system's instantaneous coefficient of performance (COP), and the resulting daily operational cost savings. Simulation results reveal that the LHTES-integrated system, when managed by a smart control strategy, successfully transfers a significant portion of the electrical demand to off-peak hours. Thus, a marked reduction in daily energy costs is achieved, and the proposed integration is seen to offer a sustainable and economically viable solution for residential demand-side management.

Keywords: Heat Pump, Phase Change Material (PCM), Thermal Energy Storage, Techno-Economic Analysis, Peak Load Shifting, Affordable & Clean Energy.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in energy demand and the necessity to combat global climate change are leading to a reshaping of energy policies around the world. Buildings, which are responsible for approximately 30% of global final energy consumption and 26% of energy-related carbon emissions, are at the center of this transformation [1]. Increasing energy efficiency in buildings and electrification of heating systems has become a strategic imperative in line with the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan [2] and 2053 Net Zero Emission targets [3], especially for developing countries with high energy dependence such as Türkiye.

Space heating constitutes the largest component of energy consumption in buildings, especially in continental and cold climate zones. Air Source Heat Pumps (ASHP), which are candidates to replace traditional fossil fuel boilers, stand out with their high efficiency potential (COP) and low carbon footprint. Heat pumps can transfer large amounts of heat with little power consumption, but they can become the largest consumers of electricity in homes.

The "Time-of-Use" tariff structure implemented by the Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA) [4] to manage these imbalances in the electricity grid and reduce end-user costs offers a significant opportunity for

demand side management (DSM). In this structure, where electricity prices are differentiated according to the time of day (Day, Peak, Night), storing energy when it is cheap and using it when it is expensive (energy arbitrage) forms the basis of economic optimization. In this context, Phase Change Materials (PCM), which have high energy storage density and provide phase change (isothermal) heat transfer at almost constant temperature, offer a more compact and efficient Thermal Energy Storage (TES) alternative compared to conventional water tanks.

Wu et al. [5] conducted field tests in severe cold climates, confirming that while ASHPs can meet heating demands even at -24.7°C , their efficiency is highly sensitive to supply water temperatures. To mitigate performance drops in such cold regions, Gao et al. [6] proposed a solar-coupled ASHP system with PCM, reporting significant efficiency gains up to 70.9% by optimizing the phase change temperature intervals. Focusing on the heat transfer mechanism, Lin et al. [7] and Du et al. [8] developed novel condensing heat storage units where the refrigerant exchanges heat directly with the PCM. Du et al. [8] highlighted that this direct integration could lower operational costs to 15.1% of conventional electric heating by leveraging peak-valley power demand, while Lin et al. [7] demonstrated that multi-stage PCM configurations could further enhance exergy efficiency. However, the integration of PCM requires careful parameter optimization; Yıldız et al. [9] experimentally showed that while PCM inclusion improves COP by 33.9% at lower tank temperatures (35°C), it can have adverse effects at higher temperatures (55°C), emphasizing the trade-off between sensible and latent heat storage. On the system configuration side, Xu et al. [10] evaluated novel layouts connecting the storage unit to the de-superheater, finding a 22-26% improvement in heating performance factors compared to conventional condenser-charged systems. Similarly, Shan et al. [11] investigated a layout for storing low-grade heat during off-peak periods. Although their system successfully shifted 2.8–3.6 kW of electrical load, they noted that heating costs could slightly increase due to heat exchanger limitations. Despite these extensive efforts on component design and hybridizations, there is still a need for a comprehensive techno-economic analysis that specifically addresses the "Time-of-Use" tariff compatibility of simple, scalable ASHP-PCM retrofits in cold climates, without requiring complex solar or multi-stage couplings.

In this study, a techno-economic analysis of the ASHP-TES integrated heating system designed for a residential house is carried out considering the climatic conditions of Yozgat province and the 3-time tariff structure of the Türkiye electricity grid. The thermodynamic balance and energy consumption of the system are analyzed with the quasi-steady-state simulation model developed within the scope of the study. The main objective is to alleviate the load on the grid by storing heat at night when electricity is cheap and using it during peak hours when electricity is expensive, minimizing the daily operating cost for the end user. The results are evaluated based on the economic savings potential and COP increase of the proposed system on both the coldest design day (-13°C) and typical winter days (-5°C).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, an integrated heating system consisting of an air source heat pump (ASHP) and a Phase Change Material (PCM) based thermal energy storage unit is investigated. The thermal and economic performance of the system is evaluated by a quasi-steady-state simulation approach based on thermodynamic equilibrium equations. A schematic view of the system is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic view of the system.

As a reference building, a detached house with a total specific heat loss coefficient ($H=UA$) of 420 W/K is considered. The indoor comfort temperature was maintained at 20 °C throughout the heating season. Based on Eq. (1), the heating load is determined to be 13.9 kW at the design outdoor temperature (T_d) of -13 °C [12]. The heating requirement of the detached house under ambient temperature conditions is evaluated using Eq. (2).

$$\dot{Q}_{hd,d} = H(T_i - T_d) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{hd} = H(T_i - T_o) \quad (2)$$

Hydronic radiators were used as the heating system distributing element. The heat transferred from the radiator to the house is modeled by the non-linear relationship between the product of radiator surface area and heat transfer coefficient (UA_{rad}) and Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD). The heating capacity of the radiator is calculated by Eq. (3-6) based on the design temperature and outdoor temperature.

$$\dot{Q}_{r,d} = UA_{rad} LMDT_{r,d}^{1.25} \quad (3)$$

$$LMDT_{r,d} = \frac{T_s - T_r}{\ln \left[\frac{T_s - T_d}{T_r - T_d} \right]} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{Q}_r = UA_{rad} LMDT_r^{1.25} \quad (5)$$

$$LMDT_r = \frac{T_s - T_r}{\ln \left[\frac{T_s - T_o}{T_r - T_o} \right]} \quad (6)$$

The radiator heating system was configured to operate with a constant water flow rate (\dot{V}_r). Under standard operating conditions, the supply and return water temperatures are typically 55 °C and 45 °C, respectively (T_s , T_r). The heating capacity delivered by the radiator water can be determined using the thermodynamic parameters given in Eq. (7-8).

$$\dot{Q}_{s,d} = \dot{V}_r \rho c_p (T_{s,d} - T_{r,d}) \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{Q}_s = \dot{V}_r \rho c_p (T_s - T_r) \quad (8)$$

The heat pump unit is modeled as a vapor compression cycle using R134a refrigerant. The system is analyzed to maintain the thermodynamic balance between the evaporator, compressor, condenser and expansion valve at each time step. The thermophysical properties of the refrigerant were determined based on instantaneous pressure and temperature values using the equations of state library (CoolProp [13]).

The TES tank is modeled using the “lumped capacitance” method. The energy balance in the storage unit is expressed as a function of time by Eq. (9):

$$E_{st}^{t+\Delta t} = E_{st} + (Q_{ch} - Q_{dch})\Delta t \quad (9)$$

Where E_{st} represents the instantaneous energy (J) stored in the tank and Δt represents the time step (seconds). In the model, a material of 200 kg mass with a phase change enthalpy (L_{PCM}) of 200 kJ/kg is used and the maximum theoretical storage capacity of the system (E_{max}) is 40 MJ (11.1 kWh). The charging and discharging thermal powers (Q_{ch} , Q_{dch}) are realized at fixed rates determined by the control strategy depending on the time period of electricity.

The operation of the system is controlled by a Demand Side Management (DSM) strategy based on the “Three-Time Tariff” structure in the Türkiye electricity grid (Table 1). The objective is to minimize the power drawn from the grid during the hours when the unit price of electricity C_{el} is high. The control logic is constructed as follows:

Off-Peak (Night) Mode: C_{el} is at its lowest level. The heat pump charges the TES tank while meeting the building load ($Q_{HP} = Q_{hd} + Q_{ch}$).

Peak Mode: C_{el} is at its highest level. By discharging the TES tank, part of the building load is covered by the stored energy, thus reducing the heat pump load ($Q_{HP} = Q_{hd} - Q_{dch}$).

Normal (Daytime) Mode: The storage unit is passive, the heat pump only covers the instantaneous building load ($Q_{HP} = Q_{hd}$).

Table 1 Three-time electricity tariff used in the simulation [4].

Period	Time	Tariff	Price (TL/kWh)
Daytime	07:00-18:00	Normal	3.1649
Peak	18:00-23:00	Peak	5.0765
Night	23:00-07:00	Off-Peak	1.6221

The total daily operating cost of the system C_{total} is calculated by Eq (10) using the total electrical power consumption $P_{el,t}$ at each time step t and the corresponding tariff price $F_{tariff,t}$:

$$C_{total} = \sum_1^{24} (P_{el,t} \Delta t F_{tariff,t}) \quad (10)$$

where $P_{el,t}$ is the sum of the power of the compressor (W_{comp}) and the additional heater (Q_{sup}), if any ($P_{el,t} = W_{comp,t} + Q_{sup,t}$). The success of the peak load shifting strategy is measured by the ‘‘Daily Savings Amount’’ determined by comparing the total cost of the integrated system with the cost of the conventional system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The techno-economic performance of the developed integrated system was analyzed under two different scenarios with reference to the climatic conditions of Yozgat province and TS 825:2024 standards. The first scenario was set as -13.0°C (Design Outside Temperature) to test the capacity limits of the heating system. The second scenario is based on -5.0°C (Typical Winter Day) average low temperature data, which reflects the general characteristics of the winter season. The key performance indicators obtained from the simulation results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Summary of techno-economic performance of the integrated heat pump-PCM system under different climate scenarios.

Parameter	Design Day (-13°C)	Typical Winter Day (-5°C)
Total Heating Load (kWh/day)	332.64	252
HP Consumption during Peak Hours (kWh)		
Base System	30.42	18.74
Integrated System	22.36	12.49
Total Energy Shifted (kWh)	8.06	6.24
Daily Operating Cost (Base System) (TL)	445.21	274.22
Daily Operating Cost (Integrated) (TL)	419.33	254.39
Daily Net Savings (TL)	25.88	19.83
Savings Rate (%)	5.81	7.23

Thermal Performance and Load Balance

Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate the 24-hour dynamic thermal behavior of the integrated system under the design day (-13°C) and typical winter day (-5°C) scenarios, respectively. In both operational scenarios, the TES unit is charged during the off-peak tariff period (23:00–07:00, indicated by the blue shaded region) when electricity

prices are lowest. The stored energy is subsequently discharged during the peak tariff period (18:00–23:00, indicated by the yellow shaded region) to alleviate the grid load.

Figure 2 24-hour dynamic performance of the integrated system at design outdoor temperature (-13°C): (a) Heat load balance and PCM contribution, (b) Compressor power consumption and system COP variation, (c) Energy level in the PCM tank, (d) Comparison of hourly operating costs under time-of-use tariff against the baseline system.

Design Conditions (-13°C): As depicted in Figure 2 the building heat load remains constant at 13.9 kW due to the severe outdoor conditions. In the baseline operation, the heat pump operates near its maximum capacity to meet this demand. However, during the peak hours, the TES unit discharges approximately 2.5 kW of thermal power (orange columns). This contribution reduces the load required from the heat pump compressor, allowing it to throttle down from ~ 7.2 kW to ~ 6.1 kW electrical consumption. Consequently, the system maintains thermal comfort without necessitating auxiliary electric resistance heating, even under design conditions.

Typical Winter Day (-5°C): Under milder climatic conditions (Figure 3), the building heat load is lower, averaging around 10.5 kW. During the discharge phase, the TES contribution represents a larger fraction of the total heating demand compared to the design day. As shown in the "Power Consumption & Performance" panel, the electrical power drawn by the compressor drops significantly from ~ 4.7 kW to ~ 3.7 kW during the peak period. This demonstrates the system's ability to maximize partial load efficiency.

Figure 3 Performance of the integrated system under typical winter day conditions (-5°C): (a) Heat load balance, (b) Compressor power and instantaneous COP, (c) PCM tank charge-discharge status, (d) Hourly cost analysis of baseline and integrated systems.

System Efficiency and Electrical Load Shifting

The integration of the LHTES unit significantly enhances the operational regime and the Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the heat pump. By offloading the compressor during the discharge phase, the system operates at a more favorable compression ratio, leading to a sharp increase in instantaneous efficiency.

- In the -13°C scenario (Figure 2): The system COP improves from a baseline of 2.1 to approximately 2.6 during the discharge period.
- In the -5°C scenario (Figure 3): A more pronounced improvement is observed, where the COP rises from 2.55 during normal operation to 3.30 during the PCM discharge phase.

This efficiency boost confirms that the TES integration not only shifts the energy usage time but also reduces the absolute energy consumption during the most critical hours.

Economic Analysis

The economic implications of the proposed system are evaluated under the "Three-Time Tariff" structure, as visualized in the bottom-right panels of both figures. The disparity between the baseline cost (red line) and the integrated system cost (blue bars) during the peak window (yellow region) highlights the effectiveness of the demand-side management strategy.

- **Cost Reduction:** The visual data indicates a substantial reduction in hourly costs. For instance, in the -13°C scenario, the hourly cost drops from over 30 TRY (baseline) to approximately 23 TRY (integrated) during peak hours. Similarly, in the -5°C scenario, the hourly cost decreases from ~ 19 TRY to ~ 12 TRY.
- **Total Savings:** The simulation results indicate that the integrated system achieves a daily operating cost saving of 5.81% on the design day and 7.23% on a typical winter day.

The widening gap between the red and blue indicators in the economic analysis charts confirms that the proposed ASHP-LHTES configuration effectively shifts the electrical load from high-cost to low-cost periods, offering a viable solution for reducing end-user utility bills while supporting grid stability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the performance of a Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage (LHTES) system integrated with an Air Source Heat Pump (ASHP) for residential heating was numerically investigated, considering the Time-of-Use (ToU) electricity tariffs in Türkiye. Based on the quasi-steady-state modeling approach conducted under the climate conditions of Yozgat province, the key conclusions are summarized as follows:

1. The integration of TES prevented the heat pump from exceeding its maximum capacity limits even under severe design conditions of -13°C . The discharge of stored energy during peak hours alleviated the load on the heat pump, minimizing the need for auxiliary heaters and enhancing operational reliability.
2. The tariff-aware control strategy successfully achieved the goal of reducing grid stress. A total electrical energy of 8.06 kWh on the design day and 6.24 kWh on a typical winter day (-5°C) was shifted from expensive peak hours to low-cost off-peak hours.
3. The system offers tangible economic benefits for the end-user. Compared to the baseline system, the integrated system achieved daily operating cost savings of 5.81% on the coldest day and 7.23% on a typical winter day.

For future work, it is recommended to simulate the annual energy performance of the system to conduct a comprehensive Return on Investment (ROI) analysis that includes the capital costs of the PCM tank and heat exchangers. Furthermore, optimization of the PCM mass and melting temperature could further increase savings rates.

THANKS AND INFORMATION NOTE

This work has been supported by Yozgat Bozok University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit under grant number FHD-2025-1650.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Energy Agency, Tracking Clean Energy Progress 2023, IEA, Paris, 2023. <https://www.iea.org/reports/tracking-clean-energy-progress-2023>.
- [2] M. of E. Republic of Turkey, N. Resources, National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2024–2030), (2024). <https://enerji.gov.tr> (accessed December 4, 2025).
- [3] U. Republic of Turkey Ministry of Environment, C. Change, Turkey's 2053 Net Zero Emission Target and Climate Strategy, (2021).
- [4] Energy Market Regulatory Authority (EMRA), Electricity Market Tariffs Regulation and 2024 Tariff Tables, (2024). <https://www.epdk.gov.tr/>.
- [5] C. Wu, F. Liu, X. Li, Z. Wang, Z. Xu, W. Zhao, Y. Yang, P. Wu, C. Xu, Y. Wang, Low-temperature air source heat pump system for heating in severely cold area: Long-term applicability evaluation, *Building and Environment* 208 (2022) 108594. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.108594>.
- [6] J. Gao, S. Li, M. Adnoui, Y. Huang, M. Yu, Y. Zhao, X. Zhang, Simulation study on thermal performance of solar coupled air source heat pump system with phase change heat storage in cold regions, *Energy* 308 (2024) 132921. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.132921>.
- [7] Y. Lin, Y. Fan, M. Yu, L. Jiang, X. Zhang, Performance investigation on an air source heat pump system with latent heat thermal energy storage, *Energy* 239 (2022) 121898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121898>.
- [8] R. Du, M. Wu, S. Wang, S. Wu, R. Wang, T. Li, Integrated heat pump with phase change materials for space heating, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 203 (2024) 114769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114769>.

- [9] Ç. Yıldız, M. Seçilmiş, M. Arıcı, M.S. Mert, S. Nižetić, H. Karabay, An experimental study on a solar-assisted heat pump incorporated with PCM based thermal energy storage unit, *Energy* 278 (2023) 128035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.128035>.
- [10] T. Xu, E.N. Humire, J.N. Chiu, S. Sawalha, Latent heat storage integration into heat pump based heating systems for energy-efficient load shifting, *Energy Conversion and Management* 236 (2021) 114042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2021.114042>.
- [11] L. Shan, A. Martin, J.N. Chiu, Techno-economic analysis of latent heat thermal energy storage integrated heat pump for indoor heating, *Energy* 298 (2024) 131291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.131291>.
- [12] Turkish Standards Institution (TSE), TS 825: Thermal Insulation Requirements for Buildings, (2024). <https://intweb.tse.org.tr/standard/standard/Standard.aspx?081118051115108051104119110104055047105102120088111043113104073099117105079120119074111082078114> (accessed December 4, 2025).
- [13] I.H. Bell, J. Wronski, S. Quoilin, V. Lemort, Pure and Pseudo-pure Fluid Thermophysical Property Evaluation and the Open-Source Thermophysical Property Library CoolProp, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research* 53 (2014) 2498–2508. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie4033999>.